

Studies on some Sulphonamidobenzimidazoles as Metal Complexing Ligands. Part-I. Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of 2-(1'-Benzenesulphonylamino-3'-methylmercapto)propylbenzimidazole

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The newly synthesised sulphonamidobenzimidazole, 2-(1'-benzenesulphonylamino-3'-methylmercapto)propylbenzimidazole (BMPBzH), functioned as a (N, N, S) terdentate ligand to form strongly paramagnetic octahedral cobalt(II) complex, $\text{Co}(\text{BMPBz})_2$, while with nickel(II) and copper(II) it functioned as a (N, N) bidentate ligand to form square planar diamagnetic $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$, and distorted octahedral paramagnetic $\text{Cu}(\text{BMPBz})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Isolation and characterisation of the ligand, BMPBzH and its complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} have been discussed. Effect of polarity of solvents on the spectral behaviour of the complexes have been studied and ligand field and nephelauxetic parameters have been evaluated.

THE newly synthesised sulphonamidobenzimidazole, viz. 2-(1'-benzenesulphonylamino-3'-methylmercapto)propylbenzimidazole (BMPBzH), structure 1, showed antibacterial activity¹ against several bacteria. Such activities were found to be enhanced profoundly in the presence of metal ions, such as Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . Study of the interaction of these metal ions with this biologically active ligand was, therefore, essential for understanding the mechanism of its antibacterial action. The present contribution describes the synthesis and characterisation of the ligand BMPBzH, its complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} , and study of the spectral and magnetic properties of these complexes.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligand: The ligand BMPBzH was synthesised by condensing *o*-phenylenediamine (3.24 g, 0.03 mol) with *N*-benzenesulphonyl methionine² (8.70 g, 0.03 mol) by fusion³ at 155°. The resultant blue sticky mass was cooled to room temperature, extracted with acetone, norited, filtered, diluted with equal volume of water and pH of the mixture

was adjusted to ≈ 8 by adding aqueous ammonia solution. BMPBzH separated as a white crystalline solid which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to needle shaped crystals, dried *in vacuo*, m.p. 182-183° (Found: C, 56.3; H, 5.3; S, 17.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$, calcd. C, 56.50; H, 5.26; S, 17.72%).

Preparation of metal complexes: Aqueous solutions of metal (Co, Ni, Cu) nitrate or sulphate (0.01 mol) were treated with ethanolic solution of BMPBzH (0.05 mol). The crimson violet Co^{2+} complex $\text{Co}(\text{BMPBz})_2$, and light pink Ni^{2+} complex $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$, separated as shiny crystals on evaporating the resulting solutions (pH ≈ 8) *in vacuo*. The blue Cu^{2+} complex $\text{Cu}(\text{BMPBz})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, however, separated at pH ≈ 4.5 . The complexes were washed with aqueous ethanol, air dried and analysed. Analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Physicochemical measurements: Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr pellet using a Unicam SP 1000 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes in different solvents were recorded with a Carl Zeiss Jena VSU-2P spectrophotometer. Diffused reflectance spectra of the solid complexes were recorded on a Cary-17 spectrophotometer in MgCO_3 phase. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature with a Gouy balance, using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were computed using Pascal's constants⁴. μ_{obs} values are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF Co^{II}, Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES WITH BMPBzH

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		% Loss at 160° (Calcd.)	μ_{obs} at 300 K B.M.
		Metal	Sulphur		
Co(BMPBz) ₂	Crimson violet	7.6 (7.57)	8.1 (8.22)	—	4.69
Ni(BMPBz) ₂	Light pink	7.5 (7.54)	8.2 (8.22)	—	Diamag
Cu(BMPBz) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Blue	7.7 (7.75)	7.8 (7.81)	4.41 (4.39)	1.84

Results and Discussion

The infrared bands at 1 340 and 1 170 cm⁻¹ due to SO₂NH group of the ligand were shifted to 1 240, 1 300, 1 255 cm⁻¹ and 1 140, 1 155 and 1 130 cm⁻¹, respectively in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes indicating the presence deprotonated sulphonamido group N-bonded to the metal ions in these complexes with considerable inter-molecular interaction through oxygen atoms of the coordinated sulphonamido groups². The C—S bands could not, however, be identified as the region 1 000-600 cm⁻¹ was obscured due to superposition of a number of bands. The bands at 3 550 (strong, sharp) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (weak) in the Cu^{II} complex were due to stretching and bending modes, respectively of the coordinated water molecules.

The μ_{obs} value of 4.69 B.M. of the Co^{II} complex at room temperature as against $\mu_s = 3.88$ B.M. for a high-spin d⁷ ion in octahedral and tetrahedral fields suggests the presence of considerable amount of orbital contribution to the magnetic moment⁷.

The electronic spectra (Fig. 1) of the Co^{II} complex Co(BMPBz)₂ in the solid state (MgCO₃ phase) and in solution with solvents of different coordinating ability consist of two main bands. One appearing at 8 500-10 500 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(ν_1) transition and the other at 17 000-20 000 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(ν_2), and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P)(ν_3) transitions. The values of 10Dq and Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameter, B, have been calculated⁸ following the weak field coupling scheme and also from the transition energy ratio ν_3/ν_1 using modified Tanabe-Sugano diagram^{9a} which was also used to deduce the position of the ν_2 band, as it could not be identified in the spectra due to the high intensity ν_3 band. Electronic spectral data of the Co^{II} complex are stated in Table 2. The ν_3/ν_1 value of 2.07-2.10 for Co(BMPBz)₂ corresponds to an octahedral Co^{II} complex^{9b}. Slight distortion from the normal octahedral geometry might have arisen due to non-identical nature of the ligand atoms. The high intensity ($\epsilon = 100-400$ dm³ cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹) of absorption of the Co^{II} complex in different solvents is partly due to the absence of centre of symmetry in the complex and partly to the interaction of d π orbitals^{9c} of the Co^{II} ion with the π -orbitals of the ligand atoms, particularly of the sulphur

Fig. 1. Electronic absorption spectra of Co(BMPBz)₂ in different media : (A, —) powder, (B, ---) dimethylsulphoxide, (C, - · -) acetone, (D, ····) dioxan and (E, - x -) dimethyl formamide.

donor atoms of the coordinated methylmercapto groups. Considerably lower value of B, (611-688 cm⁻¹) indicates appreciable covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds.

The diffuse reflectance and solution spectra of the Ni^{II} complex, Ni(BMPBz)₂ are presented in Fig. 2. The diamagnetic behaviour of the complex together with a strong single broad band around 20 833 cm⁻¹ in the solid state suggests a square planar geometry^{9d} for the complex. The broad band is probably the composite of several transitions to the cluster of levels, ¹A_{2g}, ¹B_{1g}, ¹E_g from ¹A_{1g}. The high intensity transition at 31 055 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) is probably a charge transfer band. Slow dissolution of the complex in solvents of different

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} AND Cu^{2+} COMPLEXES OF BMPBzH Medium*

	(i) $\text{Co}(\text{BMPBz})_2$					
	${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ ν_1 , cm^{-1}	${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ ν_2 , cm^{-1}	${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ ν_3 , cm^{-1}	10 Dq cm^{-1}	B cm^{-1}	ν_2/ν_1^a
MgCO_3	—	—	18 155	—	—	—
DMSO	9 090	19 492 ^a 18 891 ^b	17 543	9 801 ^a 9 805 ^b	594 ^a 611 ^b	2.10
Dioxan	8 888	18 630 ^a 18 782 ^b	17 699	9 830 ^a 9 894 ^b	655 ^a 654 ^b	2.09
DMF	8 695	18 466 ^a 18 501 ^b	17 543	9 746 ^a 9 806 ^b	650 ^a 664 ^b	2.10
Acetone	8 510	18 662 ^a 18 316 ^b	17 543	8 985 ^a 9 806 ^b	650 ^a 688 ^b	2.07

	(ii) $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$									
	${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$ (ν_1)		${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ \downarrow ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ ν_2 , cm^{-1}	${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ \downarrow ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ cm^{-1}	${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ \downarrow ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ ν_3 , cm^{-1}	B cm^{-1}	ν_2/ν_1	Dt cm^{-1}	Dq ^E cm^{-1}	Dq ^A cm^{-1}
MgCO_3	—	—	20 833	31 055 ^o	—	—	—	—	—	
DMSO	13 157	8 928	17 543	20 833	25 773	758 ^a	1.59	483	1 315	
DMF	13 071	9 090	17 391	20 746	25 000	753 ^a	1.56	455	1 307	
Py	11 111	9 523	16 260	—	22 222	653 ^a	1.58	181	1 111	

	(iii) $\text{Cu}(\text{BMPBz})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$			
	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	${}^3\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^3\text{B}_{1g}$ ν_1 , cm^{-1}	${}^3\text{B}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{B}_{1g}$ ν_2 , cm^{-1}	${}^3\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{B}_{1g}$ ν_3 , cm^{-1}
MgCO_3	17 240	—	—	—
DMSO	16 900	17 750	15 300	14 000
DMF	16 750	17 250	15 400	13 500
Py	15 000	16 200	15 250	12 500

^aGraphical value ; ^bcalculated value ; ^onot shown in Fig. 2.
^{*}DMSO \equiv Dimethylsulphoxide ; DMF \equiv dimethylformamide ; Py \equiv pyridine.

Fig. 2. Electronic absorption spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$ in different media : (A, —) powder, (B, — —) dimethylsulphoxide, (C, — . —) dimethylformamide, (D,) pyridine and (.....) Gaussian components.

coordinating ability with change of colour from pink to violet or green is indicative of change of the spin state from singlet to triplet¹⁰. Solution spectra of this Ni^{2+} complex are quite similar to those of typical octahedral complexes of the type NiL_4X_2 ¹¹⁻¹⁵, where, the ν_2 (${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$) and ν_3 (${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$) bands are not greatly affected by lowering the symmetry, while the ν_1 (${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$) band splits into two components, viz. ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_g$ having energies 10 Dq^E and $10 \text{ Dq}^E - 35\text{Dt}/4$, respectively. The transition energy ratio ν_2/ν_1 in all these cases were calculated using the energy of the transition ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ as ν_2 and the centre of gravity of ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_g$ transition energies as ν_1 . The observed ν_2/ν_1 values of 1.56-1.59 correspond to six-coordinated almost octahedral Ni^{2+} complexes. The large splitting of the ν_1 band as observed in the present case suggests *trans*^{9b} configuration ; $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$ (solvent)₂ in solution of the Ni^{2+} complex, thereby providing a tetragonal a field of D_{4h} microsymmetry around Ni^{2+} ion. The in-plane (equatorial) and out-of-plane (axial) field strengths, Dq^E and Dq^A respectively, were calculated^{9j} from tetragonal radial parameter Dt using the relation $\text{Dt} = 4/7 (\text{Dq}^E - \text{Dq}^A)$. It was found (Table 2) that Dq^E values changed only very slightly while the Dq^A values increased significantly with the increase of polarity of the solvent functioning as axial ligands. Thus, on going from pyridine (Py) to solvents of lower coordinating ability, increase of tetragonal distortion, and a consequent increase of Dt values¹⁶ were observed for the Ni^{2+} complex.

Tetragonal distortion in the complex $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$ is infinitely large, for which it is square planar and diamagnetic. One additional band in the region 20 833 and 20 746 cm^{-1} in the spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{BMPBz})_2$ in DMSO and DMF, respectively was probably due to the spin-forbidden transition, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ which gained intensity by intensity stealing¹⁷ from the closely spaced strong charge transfer band in the region 30 000 cm^{-1} .

Electronic spectra (Fig. 3) of the Cu^{II} complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{BMPBz})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the solid state (MgCO_3

Fig. 3. Electronic absorption spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{BMPBz})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in different media : (A, —) powder, (B, —○—) dimethylsulphoxide, (C, —▲—) dimethylformamide, (D, —●—) pyridine; and $B_1, B_2, B_3; C_1, C_2, C_3$ and D_1, D_2, D_3 are the Gaussian components of curves B, C and D, respectively.

phase) and in solution with solvents of different coordinating ability consist of one structureless broad band in the region 14 000–22 000 cm^{-1} . Higher transition energies were observed with weakly coordinating solvents functioning as axial ligands and the position of this band gave an useful indication of the extent of tetragonal distortion of the complex. The actual symmetry of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{BMPBz})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is very low. Considering the extreme situation with an inplane $\text{Cu}(\text{N})_4$ micro-symmetry, the point group is D_{4h} , for which the expected transitions are ${}^3E_g(d_{xy}, d_{yz}) \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2})$ (ν_1), ${}^3B_{2g}(d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2})$ (ν_2) and ${}^2A_{1g}(d_{xz}) \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2})$ (ν_3). Transition energies

of the ν_1, ν_2 and ν_3 bands have been found out by Gaussian analysis¹⁸ of the observed broad spectral bands. It was found (Table 2) that the position of the ν_2 band was practically unshifted in the region 15 250–15 400 cm^{-1} while the frequencies of ν_1 and ν_3 bands decreased on going from DMSO through DMF to Py as solvents, indicating thereby, decreased tetragonal distortion of the octahedral geometry with increased ligand field strength provided by the axially coordinating solvents.

BMPBzH, therefore, functioned as a (N, N, S) terdentate ligand in forming the octahedral Co^{II} complex, $\text{Co}(\text{BMPBz})_2$, while it functioned as a (N, N) bidentate ligand to form complexes with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , which prefer square planar geometry. A similar conclusion was also arrived at from an equilibrium study¹⁹ of the complex formation of this ligand with $\text{Co}^{II}, \text{Ni}^{II}, \text{Cu}^{II}$ and Zn^{II} .

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